

VERITY Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science

BUILDING TRUSTWORTHY SCIENCE

Trustworthy science is a fundamental prerequisite for the public to place their trust in science. It is foundational to the relationship between science and society. Under this category, VERITY presents key recommendations for building and sustaining trust in science through scientific rigour, research integrity, transparency, ethical practices, and inclusivity. These recommendations promote **alignment with high standards of scientific excellence, the delivery of tangible societal benefits, collaborative practices, and open access to scientific knowledge.**

They are grounded in and aligned with established initiatives and frameworks, including e.g. [European Research Area \(ERA\)](#), [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity \(ALLEA Code\)](#), [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#), [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#), [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#), Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) Framework, [Bonn Declaration on Freedom of Scientific Research](#), and [TRUST Code of Conduct](#).

How to support building trustworthy science?

BUILDING TRUSTWORTHY SCIENCE:

Scientific Quality, Accountability, and Sustainability

- Ensure rigorous methods, reproducibility, and methodological transparency, including in the use of AI in science.
- Promote adherence to standardised protocols and peer review to enhance the credibility and comparability of research findings.
- Mandate transparent disclosure of funding sources and potential conflicts of interest to reduce bias and foster credibility.
- Ensure stable and equitable funding, reduce researcher precarity, and implement fair review processes.
- Establish robust research management systems that delegate administrative and financial tasks to avoid overloading scientists.

Scientific Transparency, Accessibility, and Open Science

- Develop open science guidelines that are field-specific, inclusive, clear, relevant, and accessible to the general public and marginalised groups (including those with lower educational attainment, economically vulnerable individuals, and older adults).
- Promote openness in data, publications, and research practices, including the use of AI, to build transparency and enhance credibility.
- Establish a centralised portal for Research Infrastructure (RI) services to improve accessibility and public engagement.

Research Integrity and Ethics

- Develop comprehensive policies and training on ethical practices, integrity, and responsible research, including the use of AI in science, that are effective and implementable, and that align with practicalities and needs.
- Ensure independent research validation, robust quality assurance, and ethical oversight for both publicly and privately funded research and enforce consequences for violations to uphold standards.
- Adapt the ethical oversight mechanisms to evolving research contexts, including interdisciplinary, use of AI, international, and cross-sector research.

Public Engagement, Inclusivity and Benefit Sharing

- Redesign academic career structures, curricula, and incentives to value societal contributions and incentivise public trust-building efforts.
- Demonstrate and communicate real-world benefits of science in everyday life.
- Raise awareness about the importance of both basic and applied science in meeting societal goals and addressing societal challenges.
- Engage communities throughout research processes to respect local knowledge, embrace diverse perspectives, and embed values such as fairness, respect, care, and honesty into practices to address societal needs.

- Foster co-creative approaches and address power dynamics to strengthen inclusive collaboration among all stakeholders, including scientists and citizens within the ecosystem of trust in science.

DOWNLOAD VERITY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FOSTERING TRUST IN SCIENCE:

VERITY Recommendations on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/16975899>

CHECK OUT OTHER STRATEGIES:

Visit VERITY Interactive Tool with all recommendations:

<https://verityproject.eu/verity-recommendations>